

FAKE NEWS AND THEIR ROLE IN PROPAGANDA MATERIALS

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Annotation. This thesis is about feyk news today and their role in propaganda materials. Also, within the framework of this topic, the research of domestic and foreign researchers was studied and suggestions and recommendations were made to users of the social network.

Keywords: Media Education, Media, Technology, fake, phishing, media education.

INTRODUCTION

The media play a big roll in the life of every person. It also forms the picture of values, social norms, attitudes, forms of behavior, life scenarios and the world as a whole. At the same time, not only the production, but also the use of media are becoming an independent type of modern human activity. However, the media is of particular importance to young people, for whom a large part of the time is spent in the media environment, and it is here that most of the personal communication takes place. In modern society, given the roller of the media, researchers and the public are increasingly focused on the need to develop media education in preschool education, school and University at all levels of Education. Media education and media competence are important for almost all educational areas today. In addition, the media is seen as an integral part of the education sector.

Misinformation on the internet is considered surprisingly dangerous, since this misinformation has serious consequences both for those distributed and for those who receive misinformation themselves[1]. In addition, **A.G. Titova** noted, fakes can occur due to many other factors[2].

In February 2017, "**Science**" magazine made one of the most influential scientific publications in the world, "**Fake News**", a number topic. "**Scientists**" have collected **126,000** fake and truthful news that have been distributed on the social network **Twitter** for ten years. In their analysis, it was found that the lie became popular much faster than in reality [3]. The information revolution bldi a favorable ground for spreading rumors and making assumptions about individuals and public figures without checking the accuracy of the content.

“Fake news is more prevalent in our time in relation to the mediatization of society, and it is considered a phenomenon with a very large base,” **E. Shults**[4].

Despite the real threats of deep technical nologies for human rights, this technology seems to be one of the technical tools with both positive and negative effects. In this regard, the legislator is faced with the task of developing and implementing a set of measures that minimize the possibility of violating the rights of citizens[5]. The rapid spread of fake news is now a problem of the whole world. Thanks to the creation, distribution and adoption of online content, fake news is becoming a real threat. People, websites, blogs, social networks are to some extent part of the problem. Fake news affects public opinion, forms their consciousness. They are intentionally distributed by platforms or users. Users do not realize how often they are exposed to fake news[6].

Conclusion

Such a situation arises when fake news is deliberately distributed that now people do not know what and who to believe or not. In recent times, lies, fictitious messages, not only entertainment publications, internet or social networks, but also serious, Official publications are being found in reputable media. It turns out that women are more likely to watch TV than men. Men, on the other hand, are more likely to address internet media than women. Modern media technologies provide a person with enormous potential opportunities for exchanging information, “*virtual*” acquaintance with various countries and their cultures, expanding their worldview, increasing the professional and general cultural level of the individual. But, at the same time, the expansion of the media leads to an over-spread of the personality's information, psychological manipulative influences, “*virtualization of consciousness*” and the strengthening of stereotypes in interpersonal communication. This requires media education as well as increased media literacy.

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